
Genetic evaluation and utilization

OVERALL PROGRESS

RAU21-168-1-2, a promising rice variety for waterlogged areas of Bihar, India

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RAU21-168-1-2 is a derivative from the IR8/BR14 cross. It was developed at the Agricultural Research Institute, Mithapur, Patna. BR14 is a deepwater variety with good elongation capacity and submergence tolerance.

RAU21-168-1-2 was compared to BR8, the recommended rice variety for lowlands, in 15 variety trials in the waterlogged fields at 5 research stations in Bihar from 1976 to 1978.

The tall-stature BR8 culture matures in 150-155 days in the field and is moderately resistant to bacterial blight. It has short bold grains and is weakly sensitive to photoperiod.

In the variety trials, the mean yield of RAU21-168-1-2 ranged from 2.4 t/ha to 4.3 t/ha. Yields of BR8 ranged from 2.7 t/ha to 3.3 t/ha. The percentage

increase in mean yield of RAU21-168-1-2 over BR8 was 27%.

In 120 minikit demonstrations, conducted in farmers' fields all over Bihar during 1978, RAU21-168-1-2 gave 8% higher yields than BR8. RAU21-168-1-2 also has shown tolerance for waterlogging. It can withstand complete submergence for 7-10 days in the post-tillering stage. ■

Genetic divergence in indigenous varieties of rice grown in Mirzapur district, U.P., India

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The genetic divergence was assessed on the basis of D^2 statistic as per Tocher's method for 35 indigenous rice varieties that have long been grown in Mirzapur district. The varieties were grouped into nine clusters (see figure).

Eight varieties — Sugarimohar, Budhiabanko, Adamchini, Basmati, Lawangchur, Motichur, Shyamjira, and

Saro — were in cluster I. Cluster II comprised nine varieties: Sukhdas, Churamani, Kesar, Badli, Ghingi, Bishnubhog, Deula, Ramras, and Lejura. Cluster III comprised 5 varieties: Sonkharcha, Dato, Silhat, Sonachur, and Gajraj. Cluster IV comprised Jilhore, Sarekhani, Badshah Pasand, Karahani, and Meghnath. In cluster V were three varieties: Bhendkabra, Usha, and Shahdeia. Cluster VI had varieties Raikera and Bansi. The remaining three clusters — VII, VIII, and IX — had one variety each: Dhania, Jaii, and Karanga. In each case the intracluster distance was scored as "0."

Among these clusters having more than one entry, intracluster distance was lowest in cluster I and highest in cluster IV. Clusters IX and I had the highest intercluster distance between themselves, followed by clusters IX and II, and IX and IV. Intercluster distance was lowest between clusters IV and II, followed by IV and I. The remaining clusters had moderate intercluster distances. Karanga showed very high D^2 values with almost all the varieties, except with Sonkharcha and Silhat, against which it showed low D^2 values. D^2 values were

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Style

- Use the metric system in all papers. Avoid national units of measure (such as cavans, rai, etc.).
- Express all yields in tons per hectare (t/ha) or, with small-scale studies, in grams per pot (g/pot) or grams per row (g/row).
- Define in footnotes or legends any abbreviations or symbols used in a figure or table.

• Place the name or denotation of compounds or chemicals near the unit of measure. For example: 60 kg N/ha; not 60 kg/ha N.

• The US dollar is the standard monetary unit for the IRRN. Data in other currencies should be converted to US\$.

• Abbreviate names of standard units of measure when they are a number. For example: 20 kg ha.

• When using abbreviations other than for units of measure, spell out the full name the first time of reference, with abbreviations in parenthesis, then use the abbreviation throughout the remaining text. For example: The efficiency of nitrogen (N) use was tested. Three levels of N were ... or Biotypes of the brown planthopper (BPH) differ within Asia. We studied the biotypes of BPH in

• Express time, money and measurement in numbers, even when the amount is less than 10. For example: 8 years; 3 kg ha at 2-week intervals; 7%; 4 hours.

• Write out numbers below 10 except in a series containing some numbers 10 or higher and some numbers lower than 10. For example: six parts; seven tractors; four varieties. But There were 4 plots in India, 8 plots in Thailand, and 12 plots in Indonesia.

• Write out all numbers that start sentences. For example: Sixty insects were added to each cage:

Seventy-five percent of the yield increase is attributed to fertilizer use.

Guidelines

• Contributions to the IRRN should generally be based on results of research on rice or on cropping patterns involving rice.

• Appropriate statistical analyses are required for most data.

• Contributions should not exceed two pages of double-spaced, typewritten text. Two figures (graphs, tables, or photos) per contribution are permitted to supplement the text. The editor will return articles that exceed space limitations.

• Results of routine screening of rice cultivars are discouraged. Exceptions will be made only if screening reveals previously unreported information (for example, a new source of genetic resistance to rice pests).

• Announcements of the release of new rice varieties are encouraged.

• Use common — not trade — names for commercial chemicals and, when feasible, equipment.

• Do not include references in IRRN contributions.

• Pest surveys should be quantified with data, (% infection, degree of severity, etc.).

Statistical distances in 35 indigenous varieties of rice, U.P., India.

lowest for Budhiabanko and Sugarimohar, followed by Sukhdas and Churamani.

An examination of the percent contribution of each character to divergence showed grain yield as the major con-

tributor (77.8%) followed by days to maturity and days to heading. Plant height and spikelets per panicle contributed equally (1.8%) toward D^2 . Test weight contributed the least (0.5%) to D^2 . ■

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Disease resistance

Rice tungro virus resistance in medium-duration prerelease cultivars

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Cultivars of all crops performing significantly better in yield and quality than

the existing cultivars are tested in adaptive trials in farmers' fields before release. During 1980, medium-duration cultivars TNAU 15776-3, AD6380, and DPI 591 were evaluated with three standard ones — Ponni, IR20, and M. Boothy — at 12 sites in Thanjavur district, Tamil Nadu.

Since its appearance in Thanjavur in

1978, tungro has been the primary disease in rice cultivation. The medium-duration cultivars raised in adaptive trials in the district were evaluated for their relative resistance to rice tungro virus. With the 12 sites as replications, the data on the rice tungro virus were statistically scrutinized (see table).

Mean incidence of rice tungro virus (RTV) at Thanjavur District, Tamil Nadu, India.

Culture	Parentage	RTV (%) ^a	
		AV	TV
DPI591	IR1712/IR1330	4.4	12.1
AD6380	IR8/Co25	5.1	13.1
M. Boothy	Tg65/ME80	12.5	20.7
Ponni	TG65/ME80	13.8	21.8
IR20	IR262/TKM6	65.4	54.0
TNAU15776-3	ASD5/IR20	89.1	70.7
C.D. = (P = 0.05)			6.3

^aAV = actual percentage of RTV worked out. TV = transformed value (angular value) for the actual percentage.

DPI 591 and AD6380 recorded a very low tungro incidence of about 5%. That indicated their high field resistance to the disease. If released as new varieties, the two cultivars can be best utilized in the rice tungro problem areas. ■

Resistance to bacterial blight

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Rice cultivars were screened for resistance to bacterial blight disease. The plants were raised in pots containing wetland soil and in the field spaced 20 × 10 cm. Fertilizers were applied at 120-60-60 kg NPK/ha. The plants were inoculated at three stages: seedling (20 days), tillering (50 days), and boot-leaf. The disease severity was scored on a scale of 0-9. Many cultivars were rated susceptible; a few were moderately resistant.

Interestingly, ASD5 was resistant, comparable with TKM5 until tillering. IR22 and IR26 were moderately susceptible and ASD5 was resistant in the tillering stage. But ASD5 became infected in the panicle-emergence stage. Progeny of ASD5 — TNAU7124 and TNAU 15776 — also scored resistant until tillering and were moderately susceptible in the boot-leaf stage. The con-